

CONTROLLING THE FREQUENCY OF ELECTRICITY PRODUCED BY A LARGE WIND FARM

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Abstract. *The strong penetration of wind power into the power grid may threaten the operation of the power grid without proper frequency control methodologies. This paper proposes a coordinated control strategy for the active power of wind power plants to enhance their influence on the load frequency control process of power systems. The coordinated control system is designed to enable the wind power plant to participate in the load frequency control of the Hybrid Interconnected Power Systems. With the cooperation of countries and international organizations, the world's energy sector is shifting from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources [1]. Renewable energy has shown record growth in recent decades. As a major source of renewable energy, wind power installation continues to accelerate. In 2021, about 72 GW of wind power was added worldwide, bringing the cumulative total installed capacity to about 569 GW, an increase of nearly 11% compared with 2020. In addition, in 2021, the global offshore wind energy market grew by 30% compared to 2020. With the increasing penetration of wind energy in the system and the planned decommissioning of conventional fossil fuel power plants, the system exhibits less inertia and the frequency control capabilities of the system tend to deteriorate [5]. In order to maintain the reliable and safe operation of the system, frequency support from the GW is desirable or necessary for system operators in the future. However, due to the random and intermittent characteristics of wind energy, the output power and frequency of the GW are not as stable as those of conventional fossil fuel power plants. This paper discusses a wind power generation system (WGS) based on a Double Fed Induction Generator (DFIG).*

Keywords: *hybrid Power System, Wind Generator, Frequency Control, Asynchronous Generator, DFIG, Grid Side Converter.*

Introduction

To operate Hybrid Power Systems properly, it is necessary to maintain a balance between the total power generation and the total load demand, and also to consider the losses associated with the system. This situation causes the operating point of the electrical system to change over time, and as a result, deviations in the nominal frequency of the system and the scheduled power exchanges with other parts of the system may occur, which will adversely affect the operation of the system. Due to the random and intermittent characteristics of the operating wind farm, the output power of the GW is not as stable as that of conventional fossil fuel power plants. When the wind speed changes, the GW may cause two urgent problems in the frequency response process: 1. The uncertainty of the wind speed causes the GW output power to fluctuate. 2. Due to the rotation speed fluctuation caused by the unevenness of the wind speed, the GW frequency may

fluctuate, and the frequency response of the generators will not be able to suppress the frequency fluctuation of the system. Therefore, the frequency support from the WG rotors is much like a frequency dip time delay, but not a continuous frequency fluctuation control. During the WG frequency support, the system also needs to find other frequency response reserves to avoid the second frequency dip. The development of a safe frequency control strategy includes the following procedures:

1) In case of serious disturbances in the system and the failure of the WG and generator frequency response to stabilize the system frequency, a backup frequency response control based on the HVDC link is proposed to mitigate the frequency fluctuation.

2) To avoid the potential second frequency dip caused by the recovery of the WG kinetic energy, a frequency compensation control based on the coordinated control of the WG and the HVDC link is proposed to compensate for the frequency variation by distributing the frequency response reserve in different independent asynchronous power networks.

Main Part

For the proper operation of interconnected power systems, it is necessary to maintain a balance between the total power generation and the total load demand, and to take into account the losses associated with the system. This state of affairs causes the operating point of the electrical system to change over time, and as a result, deviations in the nominal frequency of the system and the scheduled power exchanges with other areas may occur, which will adversely affect the operation of the system [1]. Load frequency regulation is an ancillary service related to the short-term energy and frequency balance of power systems. It plays a central role in ensuring the power exchanges and providing the best conditions for power exchanges. The speed governor adjusts the speed of the prime mover on the turbine as the load on the generator changes[8]. This function of controlling the speed of the turbines is one of the main functions of the system. The governor setting can be changed (and therefore adjusted) according to the load to maintain the speed of the prime mover as the load on the generator changes. This is the main function of speed control and is of paramount importance in maintaining a constant frequency. Figure 1 shows the basic diagram of a Hybrid Power System.

Figure 1. Single-line diagram of Hybrid Power System

Frequency control by DFIG to coordinate inertial control, rotor speed control and blade pitch control in low, medium and high wind speed mode. Rotor speed control and blade pitch control can enable DFIG to reserve sufficient active power for frequency control[3-4].

Fig 2 Frequency regulation of DFIG-based WGS power generation

As shown in Fig. 1, this generation scheme has a variable speed wind turbine which is connected to a DFIG through a gearbox, the stator winding of the DFIG is connected to the winding of a three-phase transformer while the rotor winding is connected to an electronic power converter, better known as a Back-to-Back Converter (BBC). The BBC consists of two three-phase converters which are connected across a DC Link where the generator side converter is connected to the rotor winding providing the DC Link voltage while the Grid Side Converter (GSC) is fed from the DC Link voltage. Thus, both converters can operate as a rectifier or as an inverter depending on the direction of power flow. The BBC ensures that power is generated at the rated grid frequency and rated grid voltage regardless of the rotor speed [2]. This work focuses on the grid-side control of the converter, analyzing its two operating modes: as a constant voltage power source (rectifier mode), where the power flows from the grid to the BBC, and in the inverter mode, where the power flow is from the BBC to the grid. Vector control is used to control the GSC, and voltage and current controllers are developed, responsible for controlling the voltage on the DC_Link and managing the generated active and reactive power. The converter is verified using simulation[6-7].

GSC Converter. on the grid side.

Figure 3 shows the electrical circuit diagram of a three-phase grid and a GSC. The converter is modeled using bidirectional switches, where the ideal switch is usually created by an IGBT (insulated gate bipolar transistor) with a diode in the antiparallel position. To implement the connection of the GSC to the grid, an L-filter is used, where the inductor resistance is included[9-10].

Figure 3. Electrical diagram of a three-phase grid and grid-side converter.

Results

Variations in wind speed for different wind farms at different times result in different operating conditions for wind farms. The power that one WG can provide to participate in LFC is determined by its maximum power, which is calculated as

$$P_m = \frac{1}{2} \rho A C_p(\lambda, \beta) V^3$$

where ρ is the air density, A is the effective area swept by the wind turbine blades, V is the wind speed, C_p is the wind turbine power factor, which is a function of the blade tip speed coefficient λ and the turbine blade pitch angle β . The upper limit of the rotor speed is defined as ω_{th} . The maximum power for a WT to participate in LFC without pitch angle adjustment is defined as ΔP

$$\Delta P = P_{max} - P_{min}$$

where P_{min} is the output signal at $\omega = \omega_{th}$ and $\beta = 0$, which is defined as the critical power of the VG, which is also shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4 Power of the GW in regions with different wind speed

The unloading mode in which the active output power of the GW is greater than P_{min} is defined as the normal unloading mode, otherwise it is defined as the deep unloading mode. In the deep unloading mode, the GW is controlled by the tilt angle of the turbine to regulate the frequency. It can be seen from Fig. (3) that the maximum active output power of the GW is related to the wind speed. The wind speed has a large uncertainty and variability in both time and space, accordingly, different GWs in the wind farm are likely to have the same probability and duration of operation under a certain wind speed.

Conclusions

The power flow control of the wind power generation system is stable. This is because the current and voltage control loops are designed correctly. The results were adequate in two modes of operation of the grid-side converter, that is, the inverter mode and the rectifier mode. Using vector control technology, correct decoupling of currents from the converter is achieved, which allows full control over the active and reactive power exchanged between the wind power generation system and the grid.

REFERENCES

1. Zervos, A., Kjaer, C., Azau, S. *et al.*: ‘ Pure power -wind energy targets for 2020 and 2030’. European Wind Energy Association, Technical Report, 2011 [Google Scholar](#)
2. Bevrani, H.: ‘ *Robust power system frequency control*’ (Springer, New York, 2009) [Web of Science@Google Scholar](#)

3. Koutroulis, E., Kalaitzakis, K.: ‘Design of a maximum power tracking system for wind-energy-conversion applications’, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, 2006, **53**, (2), pp. 486–494 [Web of Science®Google Scholar](#)
4. Varzaneh, S.G., Gharehpetian, G.B., Abedi, M.: ‘Output power smoothing of variable speed wind farms using rotor-inertia’, *Electr. Power Syst. Res.*, 2014, **116**, pp. 208–217 [Web of Science®Google Scholar](#)
5. Zhu, X., Wang, Y., Xu, L. *et al.*: ‘Virtual inertia control of DFIG-based wind turbines for dynamic grid frequency support’. IET Conf. on. Renewable Power Generation, Edinburgh, September 2011, pp. 1–6 [Google Scholar](#)
6. Ramtharan, G., Ekanayake, J.B., Jenkins, N.: ‘Frequency support from doubly fed induction generator wind turbines’, *IET Renew. Power Gener.*, 2007, **1**, (1), pp. 3–9 [Web of Science®Google Scholar](#)
7. Zhang, Z., Sun, Y., Lin, J. *et al.*: ‘Coordinated frequency regulation by doubly fed induction generator-based wind power plants’, *IET Renew. Power Gener.*, 2012, **6**, (1), pp. 38–42 [Web of Science®Google Scholar](#)
8. Nian, H., Cheng, P., Zhu, Z.: ‘Direct power control of double fed induction generator without phase-locked loop in synchronous reference frame during frequency variations’, *IET Renew. Power Gener.*, 2014, **9**, (6), pp. 576–586 [Web of Science®Google Scholar](#)
9. Erlich, I., Wilch, M.: ‘Primary frequency control by wind turbines’. 2010 IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting, Minnesota, USA, 2010, pp. 1–8 [Google Scholar](#)
10. Zertek, A., Verbic, G., Pantos, M.: ‘Participation of DFIG wind turbines in frequency control ancillary service by optimized rotational kinetic energy’. 2010 7th Int. Conf. on the European Energy Market (EEM), Madrid, Spain, 2010, pp. 1–6 [Google Scholar](#)